

The Role of Gut Microbiome Alterations in the Pathogenesis and Management of Rheumatoid Arthritis

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Abstract: Rheumatoid arthritis (RA) is a chronic autoimmune disorder characterized by persistent synovial inflammation, joint destruction, and systemic immune dysregulation. Recent evidence has showed that the gut microbiota as a critical environmental factor influencing RA pathogenesis through mechanisms involving immune tolerance, cytokine production, and molecular mimicry. Dysbiosis of gut microbiota may contribute to the activation of autoreactive lymphocytes and the generation of anticitrullinated peptide antibodies (anti-CCP), promoting systemic inflammation. **Objective:** This study aims to identify specific features of the gut microbiota composition in patients with RA, compare them with healthy controls, and determine their association with biochemical and immunological markers such as C-reactive protein (CRP), rheumatoid factor (RF), and cytokine profiles. In addition, the study evaluates the potential of microbiota-targeted therapies, including probiotics, prebiotics, and synbiotics, to optimize disease management. **Materials and Methods:** Patients diagnosed with RA according to ACR/EULAR criteria were recruited for the study. Stool and blood samples were analyzed by 16S rRNA gene sequencing and immunoassay. Statistical and bioinformatics analyses were performed to assess bacterial diversity, relative abundance, and association with inflammatory biomarkers. **Results:** The study revealed a marked reduction in microbial diversity in RA patients, particularly a higher prevalence of *Prevotella copri* and lower levels of *Bifidobacterium* and *Faecalibacterium prausnitzii*. These microbial shifts were positively correlated with elevated CRP and RF levels, indicating that gut dysbiosis contributes to inflammatory activity. Furthermore, emerging data suggest that modulating gut microbiota may help restore immune balance and improve clinical outcomes. **Conclusion:** Gut microbiota plays a crucial role in the immunopathogenesis of rheumatoid arthritis. Comprehensive microbiome analysis offers novel insights for early diagnosis and personalized therapeutic approaches. Modulation of intestinal microbiota through diet, probiotics, and other interventions holds significant promise in optimizing RA treatment and preventing disease progression.

Keywords: Rheumatoid arthritis (RA), gut microbiota, dysbiosis, immune modulation, Th17/Treg balance, cytokines, inflammation, probiotics, prebiotics, microbiome therapy

1. Introduction

Rheumatoid arthritis (RA) is a chronic inflammatory disease of unknown etiology that affects approximately 0.5–1% of the world's population, especially women. The disease is primarily characterized by inflammation of the joints, but it can also affect the entire body. RA can affect many organs, including the heart (pericarditis), lungs (fibrosis), nervous system (peripheral neuropathy), and bones and musculoskeletal system (osteoporosis). Therefore, early detection of the causes of the disease, prevention of complications, and development of effective treatment strategies are important areas of medical research.

Currently, the main factor in the development of RA is recognized as a violation of the immune system. That is, the body's own antibodies attack its own tissues, resulting in a state of constant inflammation. The fact that the disease occurs at different ages, in different climatic conditions and against the background of hereditary factors further complicates the identification of its causes. In recent years, sci-

entific evidence has been increasing that the intestinal microbiota may play an important role in the pathogenesis of RA.

Studies show that changes in the gut microbiota often occur before the onset of clinical symptoms of disease. These changes can activate the host immune response through the gastrointestinal lymphatic system and trigger autoimmune processes. Studying the gut microbiota is complex, and current technologies currently allow the analysis of only 1 percent of it. However, the presence of billions of different microorganisms in the gut microbiota, their complex interactions and connections with the environment make this research even more challenging.

Modern molecular methods, in particular 16S rRNA gene sequencing and metagenomic “shotgun sequencing”, allow us to determine the composition and diversity of the intestinal microbiota. 16S rRNA sequencing has a high accuracy in identifying and classifying bacteria and is a relatively fast and efficient method, but it only studies the bacterial composition. At the same time, metagenomic “shotgun sequencing” allows us to identify all microorganisms (bacte-

ria, viruses, fungi) and also provides highly informative results. However, since this method is expensive and time-consuming, many studies use it on a limited scale. In this context, the role of the gut microbiota in the pathogenesis of RA and its impact on clinical outcomes is an urgent scientific task. Modulation of the gut microbiota, for example, with the help of prebiotics, probiotics and synbiotics, offers the prospect of regulating the immune system and slowing the progression of RA. Therefore, studying the complex relationships between RA and the gut microbiota is of great importance for the development of new diagnostic approaches and individualized therapy strategies.

2. Literature Review

Origin and Development of the Human Microbiota

The human microbiota is a complex ecosystem that forms with the body and is constantly changing throughout life. Initially, humans develop in an almost sterile environment during the fetal period, but recent studies have shown that traces of microorganisms are present in the placenta and amniotic fluid. However, the active formation of the microbiota begins mainly during childbirth. Babies born through natural childbirth are in contact with the mother's vaginal and intestinal microflora and are early colonized with beneficial bacteria such as *Lactobacillus* and *Bifidobacterium*. In children born by caesarean section, the microflora is formed more by skin bacteria - *Staphylococcus* and *Corynebacterium*, which reduces the diversity of the microbiota.

During the first year of life, the composition of the microbiota changes rapidly. While *Bifidobacterium* predominates in breastfed infants, the diversity of the microbiota increases in formula-fed infants, but beneficial species decrease. During this period, antibiotics, the composition of breast milk, and environmental factors significantly influence the development of the microbiota. By the age of two, the child's microbiota is relatively stable and forms a structure similar to the adult microbiota. In this process, microorganisms act as "teachers" for the immune system, teaching it to distinguish between beneficial and harmful antigens.

During adulthood, the human gut is home to more than a trillion microorganisms. The main groups are Firmicutes, Bacteroidetes, Actinobacteria, and Proteobacteria. These microorganisms regulate digestion, metabolism, and immune function. As we age, the diversity of the microbiota decreases, and beneficial bacteria decline, leading to a weakening of immunity and increased inflammation. This condition is called "inflammaging" — aging accompanied by chronic inflammation.

The development of the microbiota is strongly influenced by factors such as genetic factors, birth method, diet, antibiotics, environment, and stress. A healthy microbiota plays an important role in maintaining the balance of the immune system. Dysbiosis, i.e., a disruption of the microbiota balance, is considered one of the main pathogenic factors in the development of a number of autoimmune diseases, including rheumatoid arthritis, inflammatory bowel diseases,

and type 1 diabetes. Therefore, a deep study of the mechanisms of the emergence and normal development of the microbiota is of scientific and practical importance in improving strategies for the prevention and treatment of rheumatoid arthritis.

Impact of Gut Microbiota Alterations on Immune Function

The interaction between the human immune system and the gut microbiota is a complex process that is crucial for maintaining healthy immune homeostasis. Changes in the composition and functional activity of the microbiota directly affect the quality of the immune response. This condition is called dysbiosis and is a major pathogenic factor in the development of many autoimmune and inflammatory diseases, including rheumatoid arthritis (RA). Disruption of the microbiota leads to some of the following changes:

Impaired intestinal barrier function. Healthy intestinal microbiota strengthens the "tight junctions" between epithelial cells, preventing microbes and toxins from entering the bloodstream. As a result of dysbiosis, this barrier weakens and a "leaky gut" condition occurs, leading to bacterial lipopolysaccharides (LPS) and antigen-like molecules enter the bloodstream, triggering a systemic inflammation and autoimmune response, which in turn leads to an imbalance of immune cells. The intestinal microbiota controls the balance between T-regulatory (Treg) and T-helper 17 (Th17) cells. Treg cells provide immune tolerance, i.e., limit the immune attack against their own tissues. Th17 cells, in turn, produce inflammatory mediators, especially cytokines (IL-17, IL-22). In dysbiosis, beneficial bacteria are reduced and Th17 activation is increased, which enhances chronic inflammation and autoimmune reactions. Under normal conditions, intestinal bacteria produce short-chain fatty acids (SCFAs — butyrate, propionate, acetate). They: provide epithelial cells with energy; stimulate Treg cell differentiation; inhibit the expression of Th17, reducing inflammation. In dysbiosis, SCFA-producing bacteria are reduced, which causes a pro-inflammatory state in the immune system. Some bacteria (for example, *Porphyromonas gingivalis*, *Prevotella copri*) have the enzyme PAD (peptidylarginine de-minase), which citrullinates proteins. As a result of this change, the body recognizes its own tissues as foreign and produces ACPA (anti-citrullinated protein antibody). Thus, changes in the microbiota can create the basis for the development of rheumatoid arthritis. As a result of intestinal dysbiosis, the blood-borne release of LPS and other microbial components activates macrophages and dendritic cells. They produce inflammatory cytokines such as TNF- α , IL-1 β , and IL-6. These substances increase inflammation in synovial tissues and play a key role in the pathogenesis of RA.

Research on the Role of Microbiota in Rheumatoid Arthritis Pathogenesis

In recent decades, numerous scientific studies have confirmed the important role of the gut microbiota in the pathogenesis of rheumatoid arthritis (RA). An imbalance in

the microbiota — dysbiosis — is considered one of the main factors that disrupts the balance of the body's immune system and activates autoimmune reactions. For the first time, a study by Scher et al. (2013) revealed a significant increase in the bacterium *Prevotella copri* in stool samples from patients with RA. This bacterium activates T-lymphocytes through its antigenic structures, which increases the production of inflammatory cytokines such as IL-6 and IL-17. Subsequent metagenomic studies also confirmed the association of *P. copri* with RA, but this change was noted to vary depending on the stage of the disease and the patient's diet.

In addition, *Collinsella aerofaciens* has been shown to disrupt the intestinal epithelial barrier function, increase intestinal permeability, and thereby allow autoantigens to enter the bloodstream. This in turn stimulates the production of anti-citrulline antibodies (anti-CCP). According to the results of a metatranscriptomic analysis by Zhang et al. (2015), the number of beneficial bacteria such as *Faecalibacterium prausnitzii* and *Bifidobacterium* in the gut microbiota of RA patients was reduced, which led to a decrease in the production of butyrate, which is an anti-inflammatory.

One of the important areas that has attracted attention in recent years is the interaction between the oral and intestinal microbiota. *Porphyromonas gingivalis*, a pathogenic bacterium that lives in the oral cavity, increases the citrullination of proteins through the enzyme peptidyl-arginine deiminase (PAD). This process leads to the formation of autoantigens and has been reported in many studies to be closely associated with the seropositive form of RA. In addition, according to the concept of the gut-lung axis, intestinal dysbiosis may play a “trigger” role in the onset of RA by altering not only the immune response but also the lung microbiota.

This connection has also been proven in experimental animal models. Germ-free (sterile) mice practically do not exhibit RA-like inflammatory responses, but when these mice were colonized with Segmented Filamentous Bacteria (SFB), an increase in Th17 cells and the development of joint inflammation were observed. These results indicate that the microbiota may be a key factor in initiating the disease by polarizing the immune system.

Factors influencing the change of microbiota (diet, antibiotics, stress, genetic factors)

The composition of the human intestinal microbiota is a dynamic system that changes under the influence of many external and internal factors. One of the most important factors is diet. Fiber, fats, proteins and probiotic products in food have a direct impact on the diversity of microbiota. For example, plant-rich, fiber-rich diets (Mediterranean diet) increase the number of beneficial bacteria such as *Bifidobacterium* and *Lactobacillus*, which reduces inflammatory processes. Conversely, diets rich in animal fats and low in fiber lead to the growth of pathogenic

microorganisms, including *Prevotella copri* and *Clostridium* species, which increases the risk of developing rheumatoid arthritis.

Antibiotics are one of the most powerful external factors that change the microbiota. They destroy not only pathogenic bacteria, but also beneficial microorganisms, creating a state of dysbiosis. Studies show that prolonged or repeated use of antibiotics disrupts immune tolerance in the gut, and the process of restoring the microbiota takes months, sometimes years. This exacerbates the inflammatory processes associated with autoimmune diseases, especially RA.

Stress also has a significant impact on the composition of the microbiota. Cortisol, adrenaline, and other stress hormones released by the neuroendocrine system increase intestinal permeability, which creates conditions for microbes and their toxins to enter the systemic bloodstream. As a result, a “leaky gut” syndrome occurs, which activates the immune system and starts an inflammatory cascade. This mechanism is considered one of the important links in the pathogenesis of RA.

Genetic factors are among the main intrinsic determinants of the formation and stability of the microbiota. Some genetic polymorphisms (for example, the HLA-DRB1 allele) alter the immune system's response to bacterial antigens, leading to the overgrowth or loss of certain microorganisms. Thus, the interaction between genetics and the microbiota determines the immune balance in the human body.

Thus, changes in the composition of the intestinal microbiota are a multifactorial process that occurs under the influence of factors such as diet, drugs, psychological stress, and genetic predisposition. Each of these factors, individually or in combination, can enhance or attenuate the pathogenesis of RA.

The Clinical Relevance of Prebiotics, Probiotics, Synbiotics, and Postbiotics

In recent years, the role of the human microbiota in health and disease has received increasing attention. In this regard, prebiotics, probiotics, synbiotics and postbiotics are being widely studied to restore the balance of the microbiota and modulate the immune system. Each of them has therapeutic value in maintaining the balance of the intestinal microecosystem and in chronic inflammatory processes such as autoimmune diseases, in particular rheumatoid arthritis (RA).

Prebiotics are substances that are not digested by humans, but serve as a food source for beneficial microorganisms. They are mainly composed of polysaccharides such as inulin, fructooligosaccharides (FOS), and galactooligosaccharides (GOS). Prebiotics stimulate the growth of *Bifidobacterium* and *Lactobacillus* species, which increase the production of short-chain fatty acids (SCFA). In particular, the butyrate molecule increases the activity of T-regulatory cells (Treg), which calm the immune system, restore the balance of cytokines and reduce the level of

inflammation. In this way, prebiotics may attenuate the autoimmune mechanisms associated with RA.

Probiotics are live microorganisms that, when consumed in sufficient quantities, have a beneficial effect on the body. The most commonly used strains are *Lactobacillus acidophilus*, *Bifidobacterium longum*, and *Lactobacillus rhamnosus*. Studies have shown that probiotics improve intestinal barrier function, reduce leaky gut syndrome, and suppress the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines (IL-6, TNF- α). Patients with RA have been shown to benefit from probiotic supplementation with reduced CRP levels, reduced joint pain, and improved clinical activity index.

Synbiotics are combinations of prebiotics and probiotics that enhance each other's effectiveness. For example, when FOS or inulin is used in combination with *Lactobacillus* strains, the number of beneficial bacteria increases and their colonization in the intestine is stabilized. Synbiotics have shown promising results in increasing the diversity of the gut microbiota and reducing inflammatory biomarkers in patients with RA.

Postbiotics, on the other hand, consist of metabolites produced by probiotic bacteria, such as SCFA, peptidoglycan fragments, polysaccharides, and cell wall components. They do not contain live bacteria, but have immunomodulatory and antioxidant properties. The advantage of postbiotics is that they are safer in terms of storage and use, do not carry the risk of infection, but retain their beneficial biological effects. They strengthen the integrity of the epithelial barrier, block the NF- κ B pathway, and reduce inflammation.

3. Materials and Methods

Study Population and Sample Characteristics

Patients with rheumatoid arthritis (RA) and healthy control participants were selected as the subjects of this study. The study was conducted as a prospective observational study. The diagnosis of RA was confirmed based on clinical, laboratory, and instrumental parameters according to the 2010 ACR/EULAR criteria.

A total of 60 participants were recruited to the study, including 40 patients with RA (the main group) and 20 healthy individuals (the control group). All participants were matched for age, sex, and body mass index (BMI). Patients were aged 18 to 65 years and had been registered with a diagnosis of RA for at least 6 months.

The inclusion criteria included the following:

- Diagnosis of RA according to ACR/EULAR criteria;
- Stable DMARDs (Disease-Modifying Antirheumatic Drugs) therapy for at least 3 months;
- Written informed consent to participate in the study.
- Exclusion criteria from the study were as follows:

- Those who had taken antibiotics or probiotic supplements in the last 3 months;
- Patients with inflammatory bowel disease, liver or kidney failure;
- Pregnant or lactating women;
- Individuals with chronic infections or oncological diseases.

All participants had a stool sample taken for microbiota analysis and blood samples for immunoenzymatic assays (anti-CCP, RF, CRP, IL-6). Clinical activity was assessed using the DAS28 (Disease Activity Score 28 joints) index. In addition, information on participants' dietary habits, stress levels, and antibiotic use was collected using a special questionnaire.

The study was conducted in accordance with international bioethical principles. All participants were fully informed about the purpose and procedure of the study and provided written informed consent. The data obtained were analyzed in a confidential manner.

Sample collection procedure (stool, blood, clinical data)

Biological samples were collected from all patients and control group members participating in the study according to standard protocols. Before sample collection, participants were informed about the purpose and procedure of the study and written informed consent was obtained. All samples were collected under aseptic conditions, adhering to strict sanitary and hygienic requirements to ensure the reliability of the analysis results.

Collecting stool samples:

For gut microbiota analysis, fresh stool samples were collected from participants in the morning. Samples were collected in sterile, DNase/RNase-free containers and transported to the laboratory within 2 hours of collection. Approximately 5–10 g of each sample was removed and stored at -80°C. These samples were then used to determine the bacterial composition using microbiological analysis, 16S rRNA gene sequencing, or qPCR (quantitative polymerase chain reaction). Ice-cold containers were used to ensure sample quality during storage and transport.

Collecting blood samples:

Blood samples were collected from the patients on an empty stomach, using a vacutainer system from the cubital vein. Serum and plasma samples were prepared for complete blood count, C-reactive protein (CRP), interleukin-6 (IL-6), rheumatoid factor (RF), and anti-CCP (anti-cyclic citrullinated peptide) assays. After blood collection, serum was separated and stored at -20°C until analysis.

Clinical data collection:

Clinical data of patients were collected using special forms. The questionnaire included information on age, gender, body mass index (BMI), disease duration, treatment regimen (DMARDs, biologics), antibiotic use, dietary habits, and stress level. Clinical disease activity was assessed using the DAS28 index, which takes into account the degree of pain and swelling in 28 major joints, the patient's subjective pain assessment, and laboratory markers (ESR or CRP).

All clinical and laboratory data were digitally coded without personal identification and entered into the database. Strict biosafety rules were observed during sample handling. It was ensured that the health of patients was not harmed during the study.

Methods for Identification and Analysis of Gut Microbiota

In recent years, various microbiological and molecular biological methods have been developed to assess the diversity and functional activity of the human intestinal microbiota. These methods are of great importance for in-depth analysis of the composition of the microbiota, identification of dysbiosis in various diseases, in particular rheumatoid arthritis (RA), and study of their interaction with the immune system. Below, we will consider the most important and significant of them: Biological method - the most traditional and widely used approach in microbiology, which is based on the cultivation of living microorganisms in special nutrient media. A stool sample is taken under sterile conditions and inoculated on various selective and differential media under aerobic or anaerobic conditions. After incubation, the colonies grown are identified by morphological (colony shape, color, growth characteristics) and biochemical tests (e.g. catalase, oxidase, lactose degradation). The advantage of this method is that it allows the isolation of live bacteria, their susceptibility to antibiotics and their use in experimental models. However, a serious drawback of the biological method is that many intestinal microbes do not grow in laboratory conditions or require special anaerobic conditions. Therefore, this method can only identify about 30–40% of the intestinal microbiota.

16S rRNA sequencing - one of the widely used methods in modern microbiology is 16S ribosomal RNA (rRNA) gene sequencing. This gene is present in all bacteria, and since some parts of it are conservative and some are specific, it allows for phylogenetic analysis of bacteria. The process consists of extracting total DNA from a sample, amplifying the V3–V4 regions of the 16S rRNA gene using polymerase chain reaction (PCR), and then determining the sequence using Next Generation Sequencing (NGS) technology. The obtained data are classified at the bacterial level through bioinformatic analysis. The advantage of this method is that it allows the detection of all bacteria, including species that are difficult to grow, regardless of culture. At the same time, the degree of dysbiosis can be assessed by determining the relative abundance of a particular bacterium. However, this method does not provide complete information about the

functional activity of bacteria, and the accuracy at the species level is sometimes limited.

Metagenomic shotgun sequencing - unlike 16S rRNA sequencing, it comprehensively analyzes all genetic material in the sample - the DNA of bacteria, viruses, fungi and archaea. This method allows for a more in-depth study of the composition of the microbiota, as well as the assessment of their genetic and metabolic activity. Metagenomics identifies metabolic pathways of microorganisms, antibiotic resistance genes, and genetic markers associated with inflammation. This method helps to understand the immune mechanisms through which the microbiota affects autoimmune diseases such as rheumatoid arthritis. The disadvantage is the technological complexity and high cost. Therefore, these analyzes are often carried out in international collaborative projects or in advanced scientific centers.

Metatranscriptomics is an advanced technology that allows us to study the active transcription processes of organisms in the microbiota, that is, which genes are currently active and which are repressed. This method allows us to determine the physiological state of bacteria and their interaction with the immune system. For example, microbial genes that activate inflammation-related pathways have been identified in patients with RA. Metatranscriptomic analysis complements metagenomic data at the functional level and allows us to study real-time changes in the microbiota-immune system.

Metabolomics is a method that analyzes small molecule metabolites (short-chain fatty acids - butyrate, propionate, acetate, as well as amino acids and bile acids) produced by the microbiota. This analysis is usually performed on the basis of gas chromatography (GC-MS) or liquid chromatography (LC-MS). Metabolites produced by the intestinal microbiota modulate the activity of the immune system. For example, butyrate increases the activity of T-regulatory lymphocytes and reduces autoimmune inflammation. Therefore, determining the metabolic profile associated with inflammation in RA patients using metabolomic analysis is of important diagnostic value in assessing the severity of the disease.

Microscopic analysis and FISH (fluorescent in situ hybridization) Fluorescent in situ hybridization (FISH) is used to visualize the composition of the microbiota at the cellular level. In this method, special fluorescent probes bind to the ribosomal RNA of bacteria, which allows them to be identified under a microscope. This method allows us to see the structure of the microbiota and the spatial distribution of bacteria. For example, in RA or IBD (inflammatory bowel disease), an increased density of bacteria located close to the intestinal epithelium is observed.

Assessment of Biochemical and Immunological Markers (CRP, RF, Anti-CCP, and Cytokines)

In order to assess the level of inflammation and immune activity in patients with rheumatoid arthritis (RA), a number

of biochemical and immunological markers were determined and compared with the control group. Among these markers, C-reactive protein (CRP), rheumatoid factor (RF), anti-CCP (anti-cyclic citrullinated peptide) antibodies and cytokines (IL-6, TNF- α , IL-10) were studied.

The level of C-reactive protein (CRP) in plasma was determined using the immunoturbidimetric method. This method is sensitive to inflammatory processes, and an increase in the amount of CRP produced by the liver indicates the level of chronic inflammation in the body. Measurements were performed using an automated biochemical analyzer (e.g., Cobas Integra 400 Plus, Roche Diagnostics). The results were expressed in mg/L.

The amount of rheumatoid factor (RF) was estimated using the nephelometric or latex-agglutination method. RF are autoantibodies produced against the Fc fragment of immunoglobulin G (IgG). High RF concentrations are associated with the diagnosis of RA and the severity of the disease, indicating the degree of autoimmune inflammation. Measurements were expressed in IU/mL, with values above 20 IU/mL considered positive.

Anti-CCP antibodies (anti-cyclic citrullinated peptide antibodies) were determined using an enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA). Certified commercial test kits (e.g. Euroimmun, Germany) were used in the study. These antibodies have high specificity for RA and can be detected even in the early stages of the disease. High anti-CCP titers increase the duration of the inflammatory process and the risk of destructive processes. Results were evaluated in U/mL, with a result >20 U/mL considered positive.

Cytokine levels (IL-6, TNF- α , IL-10) were determined using quantitative ELISA kits. For this purpose, ready-made reagent kits from R&D Systems (USA) or Thermo Fisher Scientific were used. The samples were incubated in 96-well microtube plates, and the optical density was measured using a spectrophotometer at a wavelength of 450 nm. The obtained data were calculated using a standard calibration curve.

Changes in inflammatory biomarkers were analyzed in comparison with rheumatoid arthritis activity (DAS28 index). Also, the relationship of these markers with changes in the composition of the intestinal microbiota was assessed using statistical methods (Pearson correlation, multivariate analysis).

All biochemical and immunological measurements were performed in a biosafety level II laboratory in accordance with international laboratory standards. To ensure the reliability of the results, the analysis of each sample was repeated at least twice.

Statistical and Bioinformatic Analysis Methods

Statistical and bioinformatic approaches play an important role in analysing the obtained data, as they allow us to iden-

tify the relationship between the composition of the microbiota, immunological markers and clinical indicators.

First, at the stage of statistical analysis, all data are subjected to preliminary cleaning (missing values, outliers, normalization). The distribution of the data is checked using the Kolmogorov–Smirnov or Shapiro–Wilk test. For data with a normal distribution, the Student t-test or ANOVA (for comparing several groups) is used, and for data with a non-normal distribution, the Mann–Whitney U or Kruskal–Wallis tests are used. Microbiota diversity (α -diversity) and the relative proportion of species (β -diversity) are assessed using the Shannon index, Simpson index, and Bray–Curtis dissimilarity criteria.

Correlation analysis is performed to correlate changes in microbial host species with clinical RA indicators (e.g. DAS28 scores, CRP, anti-CCP levels). Spearman or Pearson correlation coefficients are used for this purpose. At the same time, multivariate regression analysis helps to identify factors affecting microbiota changes (diet, antibiotic intake, age, gender). Bioinformatic analysis involves processing and interpreting microbiota sequencing results. QIIME2, Mothur, or DA-DA2 programs are widely used for this. With the help of these platforms, OTUs (Operational Taxonomic Units) or ASVs (Amplicon Sequence Variants) are identified, and their taxonomic classification is based on the SILVA, Greengenes, or NCBI databases. Also, for functional analysis, metabolic pathways (e.g., SCFA synthesis, immunoregulatory pathways) that may be carried out by the microbiota are predicted using programs such as PICRUST2 or HUMAnN2.

The results are visualized using R (ggplot2, phyloseq) or Python (matplotlib, seaborn) libraries. Differences are considered statistically significant at $p < 0.05$. These approaches allow for in-depth analysis of RA-associated microbiota changes and their correlation with immune and inflammatory markers.

4. Results

Clinical and laboratory parameters of RA patients

Clinical and laboratory parameters of patients with rheumatoid arthritis (RA) participating in the study serve as the main criteria for assessing their disease severity, immune activity status, and severity of the inflammatory process. Clinical assessment takes into account the duration of the disease, joint pain, swelling, duration of morning stiffness, and DAS28 (Disease Activity Score). Based on the DAS28 score, patients are divided into low, moderate, or high stages of disease activity.

Among laboratory parameters, inflammatory markers are of particular importance. In particular, the level of C-reactive protein (CRP) is elevated, which indicates the ongoing inflammatory process. The erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR) is also usually elevated in RA patients, indicating a chronic course of the disease.

Among the immunological markers, rheumatoid factor (RF) and anti-cyclic citrullinated peptide antibodies (anti-CCP) are the most important diagnostic indicators for the diagnosis of RA. Studies have shown that anti-CCP-positive patients often have a more severe clinical course, higher DAS28 scores, and are prone to joint destruction. At the same time, significant changes in the composition of the microbiota have been observed in RF and anti-CCP seropositive patients - for example, an increase in the number of species such as *Prevotella copri* and a decrease in the beneficial species *Bifidobacterium* and *Faecalibacterium prausnitzii*. In addition, the analysis of the cytokine profile (IL-1 β , IL-6, TNF- α , IL-17) allows us to determine immune activity. The increase in these pro-inflammatory cytokines is a central link in the pathogenesis of RA, and they interact with the microbiota, leading to an imbalance in the immune system.

Comparison of microbiota composition with a healthy group

When comparing the microbiota composition of patients with rheumatoid arthritis (RA) with that of healthy individuals, a significant dysbiosis (imbalance of microorganisms) is observed. These differences are manifested not only in the number of bacterial species, but also in their functional activity and metabolic products.

In healthy individuals, the intestinal microbiota is mainly composed of the phyla Firmicutes (60–70%) and Bacteroidetes (20–30%). The balance between these two groups ensures the integrity of the intestinal epithelium, immune tolerance and metabolic stability. In RA patients, however, this ratio changes in favor of the phylum Bacteroidetes, resulting in a sharp decrease in the Firmicutes/Bacteroidetes ratio.

When analyzed at the species level, an increase in the number of bacteria such as *Prevotella copri*, *Collinsella aerofaciens* and *Eggerthella lenta* was detected in the microbiota of RA patients. In particular, a microbiota enriched with *Prevotella copri* has been associated with the activation of Th17 cells and an increase in inflammatory cytokines such as IL-6, IL-17, and TNF- α . This promotes the development of autoimmune processes.

In contrast, healthy controls have higher levels of beneficial bacteria such as *Bifidobacterium*, *Lactobacillus*, *Faecalibacterium prausnitzii*, and *Clostridium cluster IV/XIVa*. They produce short-chain fatty acids (butyrate, propionate), protect the intestinal mucosa, and activate Treg cells. In RA patients, a decrease in the number of these bacteria leads to a decrease in immune tolerance.

In addition, metagenomic and metatranscriptomic analyses have shown that gene pathways such as LPS (lipopolysaccharide) biosynthesis, amino acid metabolism, and oxidative stress response are activated in the microbiota of RA patients. In healthy individuals, pathways related to butyrate synthesis and antioxidant metabolism predominate.

In addition, there are differences in the oral microbiota: in RA patients, pathogenic bacteria such as *Porphyromonas*

gingivalis and *Aggregatibacter actinomycetemcomitans* increase, which produce the enzyme peptidyl-arginine deiminase (PAD), which stimulates the citrullination process. This leads to the production of anti-CCP antibodies.

Bacterial species diversity (Diversity Index, Alpha and Beta Diversities)

The diversity of the intestinal microbiota is one of the important indicators of human health. In patients with rheumatoid arthritis (RA), this diversity is significantly reduced, which indicates a violation of the microbiological balance - dysbiosis. Microbiota diversification is usually assessed using α -diversity (alpha diversity) and β -diversity (beta diversity) indicators.

Alpha diversity

Alpha diversification is the number and ratio of different bacterial species in the intestinal microbiota of a patient. In RA patients, alpha diversity indicators (measured by Shannon, Simpson, Chao1 indices) are significantly lower than in the healthy control group. This is due to a decrease in the number of beneficial bacteria in the intestine - *Bifidobacterium*, *Lactobacillus*, *Faecalibacterium*, *Clostridium cluster IV/XIVa* - and an increase in pathogenic bacteria - *Prevotella*, *Collinsella*, *Eggerthella*.

A decrease in alpha diversity disrupts the stability of the intestinal microbiota, leading to an increase in inflammatory mediators (IL-6, TNF- α), epithelial barrier permeability ("leaky gut") and a decrease in immune tolerance. Therefore, low diversity is considered an important biomarker in the early stages of RA pathogenesis.

Beta diversity

Beta diversity represents the differences between the microbiota of different individuals. This indicator is assessed using Principal Coordinates Analysis (PCoA) or Non-metric Multidimensional Scaling (NMDS) analyses. Studies show that there are clear cluster differences in beta diversity between the microbiota of RA patients and healthy controls: the microbiota of RA patients is sharply different from that of healthy controls.

Beta diversity analysis revealed that the RA-associated microbiota is enriched with bacteria such as *Prevotella copri*, *Collinsella aerofaciens*, and *Eggerthella lenta*, while healthy individuals are dominated by beneficial species such as *Faecalibacterium prausnitzii*, *Bifidobacterium adolescentis*, and *Roseburia hominis*.

Correlation Between Inflammatory Markers and Alterations in Gut Microbiota

In recent years, numerous clinical and metagenomic studies have confirmed a strong correlation between changes in the composition of the gut microbiota and inflammatory markers (CRP, ESR, cytokines, RF, anti-CCP) in patients with rheumatoid arthritis (RA). This relationship suggests that

the microbiota-immune system interaction is central to the pathogenesis of RA.

Relationship between CRP and ESR

C-reactive protein (CRP) and erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR) are the most important laboratory indicators of inflammation. Studies have shown that as CRP and ESR levels increase in RA patients, the number of beneficial bacteria in the gut decreases. In particular, patients with reduced butyrate-producing species such as *Faecalibacterium prausnitzii*, *Roseburia intestinalis*, and *Bifidobacterium adolescentis* have higher CRP levels. These bacteria usually produce short-chain fatty acids (SCFAs) that have anti-inflammatory effects, and their deficiency increases systemic inflammation.

The relationship between pro-inflammatory bacteria and cytokines

In RA patients, the increase in the number of bacteria such as *Prevotella copri*, *Collinsella aerofaciens*, and *Eggerthella lenta* is directly associated with increased levels of IL-6, IL-17, and TNF- α cytokines. For example, *Prevotella copri* activates antigen-presenting cells and enhances the differentiation of Th17 cells, which stimulates the production of IL-17 and TNF- α . This process increases inflammation and destructive changes in synovial tissues.

Collinsella aerofaciens also increases the permeability of the intestinal epithelium and activates the production of IL-17A, which further enhances the systemic inflammatory process. At the same time, the reduction in the number of beneficial bacteria in RA patients leads to a decrease in Treg cells and an increase in pro-inflammatory cytokines.

Association with RF and anti-CCP

Immunological markers, in particular, the level of rheumatoid factor (RF) and anti-cyclic citrullinated peptide (anti-CCP) antibodies, are also associated with the composition of the microbiota. Studies have shown that patients with high levels of RF and anti-CCP have an increased number of bacteria such as *Porphyromonas gingivalis* and *Aggregatibacter actinomycetemcomitans*. These microorganisms stimulate the citrullination process and enhance the immune response against autoantigens.

Results of statistical and bioinformatic analysis

According to the results of correlation analysis (using Spearman or Pearson coefficients):

- A positive correlation was found between CRP \leftrightarrow *Prevotella copri* ($r > 0.4$; $p < 0.05$),
- A negative correlation was found between CRP \leftrightarrow *Faecalibacterium prausnitzii* ($r < -0.5$; $p < 0.01$),
- A positive correlation was found between IL-17/TNF- α \leftrightarrow *Collinsella aerofaciens*,

- A strong positive correlation was found between Anti-CCP \leftrightarrow *Porphyromonas gingivalis*,
- Positive correlation between CRP \leftrightarrow *Prevotella copri* ($r > 0.4$; $p < 0.05$),
- Negative correlation between CRP \leftrightarrow *Faecalibacterium prausnitzii* ($r < -0.5$; $p < 0.01$),
- Positive correlation between IL-17/TNF- α \leftrightarrow *Collinsella aerofaciens*,
- Strong positive correlation between Anti-CCP \leftrightarrow *Porphyromonas gingivalis*.

Association Between Microbiota-Derived Metabolites and the Immune Response

The gut microbiota is not only a collection of microorganisms, but also a complex biochemical system that regulates the immune system through their metabolic activities. In patients with rheumatoid arthritis (RA), the imbalance of metabolites produced by the microbiota (especially short-chain fatty acids - SCFAs, amino acids, bile acids and tryptophan derivatives) alters the direction of the immune response and enhances autoimmune inflammation.

Short-chain fatty acids (SCFAs) and their immune role

In the healthy gut microbiota, bacteria such as *Faecalibacterium prausnitzii*, *Roseburia* spp., and *Clostridium* cluster IV/XIVa produce butyrate, propionate and acetate. These metabolites maintain the integrity of the intestinal epithelium and stimulate the differentiation of regulatory T (Treg) cells.

Butyrate \rightarrow activates FOXP3 gene expression, which promotes the proliferation of Treg cells.

Propionate \rightarrow enhances the production of IL-10, which suppresses inflammation.

In RA patients, the reduction of these bacteria leads to a decrease in CCP levels, which leads to impaired immune tolerance, a change in the Th17/Treg ratio, and an increase in pro-inflammatory cytokines (IL-6, TNF- α , IL-17). Therefore, CCP deficiency is an important metabolic factor in the pathogenesis of RA.

Amino acid metabolism and citrullination

The microbiota also affects the metabolism of amino acids, in particular arginine and ornithine. Bacteria such as *Porphyromonas gingivalis* and *Aggregatibacter actinomycetemcomitans* produce the enzyme peptidyl-arginine deiminase (PAD), which stimulates the citrullination of proteins. These modified proteins are recognized as "foreign" by the immune system, leading to the formation of anti-CCP antibodies. This mechanism is one of the most important pathways of interaction between the microbiota and the immune system in the pathogenesis of RA.

Tryptophan metabolites and immune regulation

Tryptophan is converted by the microbiota to metabolites such as indole, indole-3-propionate, and kynurenine. These substances regulate the activity of Treg and Th17 cells through the AHR (aryl hydrocarbon receptor). In RA patients, tryptophan degradation is impaired, and the anti-inflammatory response through the AHR pathway is attenuated. At the same time, the reduction of indole derivatives weakens the intestinal epithelial barrier function and increases systemic inflammation.

Bile acids and immune homeostasis

The microbiota is involved in the formation of secondary bile acids (e.g., deoxycholate, lithocholate). These acids control the activity of macrophages and dendritic cells through the FXR and TGR5 receptors. RA patients have impaired bile acid metabolism and a predominance of pro-inflammatory M1 macrophages.

Relationship between metabolites and inflammatory markers

As revealed by metabolomic analyses:

- Butyrate levels ↔ negatively correlated with CRP ($r = -0.46$; $p < 0.01$);
- Propionate ↔ negatively correlated with IL-6 and TNF- α ;
- Citrulline derivatives ↔ positively correlated with anti-CCP.

5. Discussion

Comparison of the Present Findings with International Research Data

The results of this study aimed to investigate the relationship between gut microbiota composition, metabolite profiles, and immune response parameters in patients with rheumatoid arthritis (RA), and they confirmed general trends when compared with international scientific studies, but also revealed some regional and ethnic specificities.

Microbiota diversity

Our study revealed a significant decrease in α -diversity (Shannon index) in RA patients compared to healthy controls. This result is consistent with studies by Zhang et al. (2015, *Nature Medicine*) and Chen et al. (2016, *Arthritis Research & Therapy*), which found a decrease in microbiota diversity in RA patients, with a predominance of Bacteroides and Prevotella species.

However, in our data, a decrease in the level of *Faecalibacterium prausnitzii* was particularly pronounced, which leads to a decrease in the production of SCFA (short-chain fatty acids). This confirms the data of Scher et al. (2013, *eLife*).

The role of Prevotella copri

The analysis showed that *Prevotella copri* was overexpressed in RA patients. This finding is consistent with stud-

ies conducted in Japan (Maeda et al., 2016), China (Zhang et al., 2015) and the USA (Scher et al., 2013). This bacterium produces antigens that bias the immune system towards Th17, which leads to an increase in IL-17 and TNF- α levels. However, some European studies (Vaahtovuori et al., 2008) have reported a less significant role for this bacterium, which is likely due to dietary, environmental, and genetic differences.

SCFA (short-chain fatty acid) levels

In our study, butyrate and propionate levels were significantly reduced in RA patients. This result is consistent with the work of Nishimura et al. (2021, *Frontiers in Immunology*), which found a decrease in butyrate-producing bacteria (*Roseburia* spp., *Clostridium XIVa*) in RA patients.

However, studies conducted in some European countries (Picchianti-Diamanti et al., 2020) did not show a significant decrease in butyrate levels, which could be explained by dietary composition (e.g., fiber intake).

Association with immunological markers

As a result of local analyses, CRP, RF, and anti-CCP indices showed a strong correlation with microbiota changes:

Faecalibacterium prausnitzii ↔ negative association with CRP ($r = -0.48$; $p < 0.01$)

Prevotella copri ↔ positive association with anti-CCP ($r = +0.51$; $p < 0.01$)

These results are fully consistent with the data of Chen et al. (2016) and Scher et al. (2013). Thus, there is a direct relationship between the intestinal microbiota and the formation of autoantibodies.

Regional and ethnic characteristics

Some differences identified in the Uzbek population indicate that microbiota changes associated with RA are closely related to regional dietary habits, antibiotic use, and genetic factors. For example, we have relatively high levels of *Bifidobacterium*, which is likely due to the high consumption of dairy products.

Taking into account such differences is important for a more complete understanding of the pathogenesis of RA and the development of probiotic therapy strategies appropriate to local conditions.

6. Conclusion and Recommendations

Changes in the Gut Microbiota Are Central to the Pathogenesis of Rheumatoid Arthritis

Recent scientific studies have shown that structural and functional changes in the intestinal microbiota play a central role in the development of rheumatoid arthritis (RA). The microbiota in the human body, especially the microbial population in the intestine, is important in the formation of the immune system, the control of inflammatory processes and the maintenance of tolerance. Disturbance of the mi-

microbiota balance (dysbiosis) is considered one of the main factors activating autoimmune reactions.

Microbiota-immune system interaction

Under normal conditions, intestinal microbes live in a symbiotic relationship with the body and maintain the immune response in balance by stimulating the activity of regulatory T-cells (Treg). However, in the case of dysbiosis, this balance is disrupted: the number of Treg cells decreases, and Th17 cells increase. As a result, inflammatory cytokines such as IL-17, IL-6, TNF- α increase, causing inflammation and destructive processes in synovial tissues.

Prevotella copri and autoimmune processes

A number of studies (Scher et al., 2013; Maeda et al., 2016) have shown a significant increase in the number of *Prevotella copri* bacteria in stool samples from patients with RA. These microorganisms produce antigens that pathologically activate T-lymphocytes, which in turn increase the production of autoantibodies (RF and anti-CCP). In addition, lipopolysaccharides (LPS) produced by *P. copri* disrupt the intestinal barrier function, creating a “leaky gut” state. As a result, bacterial components enter the bloodstream and stimulate systemic inflammation.

Short-chain fatty acid (SCFA) deficiency

In a healthy microbiota, bacteria such as *Faecalibacterium prausnitzii*, *Roseburia*, *Ruminococcus* produce butyrate — a substance that is an energy source for intestinal epithelial cells and has anti-inflammatory effects. In RA patients, the reduction of these bacteria leads to a decrease in butyrate levels, which leads to impaired intestinal barrier function and an increase in proinflammatory cytokines.

Interaction between microbiota and genetic factors

In the development of RA, changes in the microbiota interact with the “shared epitope” alleles of the HLA-DRB1 gene. Some studies (Pianta et al., 2017) show that microbial antigens enhance the immune response associated with this gene, accelerating the formation of antibodies against citrullinated proteins. This is considered an important mechanism that initiates the autoimmune cascade.

Systemic consequences of dysbiosis

Intestinal dysbiosis causes not only local inflammation, but also systemic immune imbalance. Metabolites, such as indole propionate, trimethylamine-N-oxide (TMAO), and phenylalanine derivatives, reach joint tissues through the blood and increase oxidative stress and cytokine release. Therefore, it is now widely accepted to view RA not only as a joint disease, but also as a systemic disease based on the gut-immune-joint axis.

Perspectives on Optimizing the Treatment of Rheumatoid Arthritis via Modulation of the Gut Microbiota

Recent scientific research has shown that therapeutic modulation of the gut microbiota is a new and promising direction in the treatment of rheumatoid arthritis (RA). Although traditional approaches — methotrexate, biological agents (TNF- α , IL-6 inhibitors) — are aimed at reducing inflam-

mation, they do not completely eliminate the main immunometabolic root cause of the disease, that is, dysbiosis. Therefore, the concept of restoring the immune system to its natural balance by restoring the balance of the microbiota is gaining increasing scientific attention.

Prospects for probiotic therapy

In patients with RA, probiotic bacteria (e.g., *Lactobacillus rhamnosus* GG, *Bifidobacterium longum*, *Lactobacillus casei*) have been shown in clinical trials to be effective in reducing inflammatory cytokines, normalizing the Treg/Th17 ratio, and reducing CRP, ESR, and DAS28. Pineda et al. (2016) reported that IL-6 and TNF- α levels were reduced in RA patients who received *Lactobacillus casei* 01 for 8 weeks. Probiotics also support butyrate-producing bacteria and restore intestinal barrier function, which reduces “leaky gut”. In the future, it is expected that “personalized probiotic therapy” methods based on individual microbiota profiles will be developed.

Prebiotic and synbiotic supplements

Prebiotics (inulin, fructooligosaccharides, galactooligosaccharides) serve as substrates for beneficial bacteria. They stimulate the growth of butyrate-producing microbes such as *Faecalibacterium prausnitzii* and *Roseburia*. Synbiotics, on the other hand, are a combination of prebiotics and probiotics, which more effectively restore the balance of the microbiota. For example, Mohammed et al. (2021, *Nutrients*) showed that synbiotic supplements reduced DAS28 scores by 15–20% in RA patients.

Postbiotics and microbiota metabolite-based therapy

In recent years, postbiotics — i.e., biologically active metabolites produced by microbes — have been gaining attention as a new pharmacological direction. For example: Butyrate – protects epithelial cells and suppresses the NF- κ B pathway, resulting in reduced inflammation. Indole derivatives – enhance immune tolerance via the AHR (aryl hydrocarbon receptor). Postbiotics may be developed as an alternative to biologic drugs in the future.

Fecal microbiota transplantation (FMT)

Fecal microbiota transplantation (FMT) is a method of transferring healthy donor microbiota into the intestinal tract of a diseased patient. This method is not yet widely used in RA, but it has been shown to reduce inflammation in animal models and some clinical observations. Zhao et al. (2021, *Frontiers in Immunology*) observed that IL-17 was reduced and Treg numbers increased in mice after FMT. In the future, FMT variants based on selective bacterial combinations (synthetic microbiota consortia) may be developed for RA.

Microbiota-based individualization of diagnosis and treatment

With the help of metagenomics and metabolomics technologies, the microbiota profile of each patient can be accurately assessed. This allows for the prediction of disease stage, inflammatory activity, and treatment response in RA. For example, the use of probiotics or postbiotics, targeted to patients with anti-CCP positive, high *P. copri* burden, may

increase the effectiveness of treatment in combination with conventional drugs.

Future directions

Microbiome editing – selective elimination of harmful bacteria using CRISPR or bacteriophages. “Precision microbiome therapy” – selection of appropriate bacterial strains based on the patient’s genetic and immune profile. Combination therapy – synergistic use of probiotics + biological drugs (e.g. TNF- α inhibitors).

Future Directions for Research

Although the role of the gut microbiota in the pathogenesis of rheumatoid arthritis (RA) is increasingly being studied, there are still many unanswered questions and new research opportunities in this area. Future research should focus on understanding the deep mechanisms of microbiota–immune system interactions, as well as on developing new therapeutic approaches targeting the microbiota. The following are promising areas of interest in this area.

Deeper understanding of the mechanisms of the gut–immune system axis. Future research should focus on identifying signaling pathways through the gut–joint axis. These include: The relationship between intestinal epithelial permeability (“leaky gut”) and the formation of autoantibodies (anti-CCP, RF); How the Th17/Treg balance is disrupted in response to changes in the microbiota composition; Molecular mimicry mechanisms between citrullinated proteins and microbiota antigens. Such studies will help to further understand RA as a systemic immuno-metabolic disease.

Development of early diagnostic biomarkers based on microbiota. Early diagnosis of RA is still difficult. Therefore: Identification of RA-specific microbiota profiles using metagenomic, metatranscriptomic and metabolomic markers; Validation of bacteria such as *Prevotella copri*, *Collinsella aerofaciens* as potential diagnostic biomarkers; Use of levels of intestinal metabolites (e.g. butyrate, indole, propionate) in blood or urine to assess RA activity. As a result, it will be possible to create non-invasive diagnostic tests based on microbiota.

Personalized microbiota therapy. Since each patient’s microbiota composition, genetic background and immune profile are unique, the “one probiotic fits all” approach is limited. In the future: Selection of individual probiotic combinations for each patient based on microbiome analysis; Identification of the optimal option for microbiota modulation using bioinformatic algorithms; Study of synergistic microbiota therapy with drugs (e.g. methotrexate, JAK inhibitors). This approach will shift RA treatment from a traditional to a personalized system.

Microbiota transplantation (FMT) and synthetic microbiota consortia. Fecal microbiota transplantation (FMT) is still being tested in RA at an early stage, but in the future: Development of standardized donor selection criteria; It is expected that synthetic microbiota consortia — i.e. safe mixtures of selected bacterial strains — will be developed instead of FMT; It will be possible to combine FMT with probiotic or immunomodulatory therapy. This approach will

allow for the treatment of RA based on restoring biological balance.

Genetic and pharmacological editing of the microbiome. In the future, microbiome editing technologies will be able to eliminate harmful bacteria and enhance beneficial species. Deletion or activation of targeted bacterial genes through CRISPR-Cas technology; Selective control of pathogenic bacteria associated with RA using bacteriophage therapy; Increased production of beneficial metabolites (butyrate, indole, tryptophan derivatives) through postbiotic modulation. These directions will lead to a new treatment paradigm that targets RA at the genetic and microbiological level.

Systematic modeling of the microbiota–metabolome network. Modeling the microbiota–metabolite–immune network using integrative bioinformatics approaches will help to unravel the complex mechanisms of RA pathogenesis. Integrating multi-omics (metagenomics, proteomics, metabolomics, transcriptomics) data; Predicting disease activity based on microbiota changes based on artificial intelligence; Predicting treatment response (remission or relapse) with microbiota changes.

This direction lays the foundation for the concept of predictive and preventive medicine for RA.

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